

Reproducing SetRank

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this research report is to reproduce the results of "Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach", by Shen et al. [1]. We will discuss the problems, when reproducing this paper and evaluate the results of the proposed ranking approach by ourselves. Shen and his colleagues presented an unsupervised ranking approach for entity set search and claimed that their approach is significantly better, when being compared to four state of the art baseline algorithms (BM25, LM-DIR, LM-JM, IB). Furthermore, they also state, that their model selection algorithm effectively chooses the most suitable parameter settings for their unsupervised ranking framework to achieve the best query ranking possible for a given data set.

KEYWORDS

Entity-Set Aware Search, Unsupervised Ranking Model, Unsupervised Model Selection, Literature Search, Reproduction

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1 INTRODUCTION

A desirable characteristic of scientific research is to allow the reproduction of experiments to verify the published results. In IR research it is hard to compare results, as often the code or data set is not published alongside with the paper or special settings or environments are needed.

In this report we want to recreate the performed experiments of "Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach" by Shen et al. [1], which has been accepted at the European Conference on Information Retrieval in 2018. We will discuss our approach to reproduce the experiment and describe all necessary steps, which need to be performed, before the source code is runnable and it is possible to recreate certain experiments. Furthermore, we will compare our results with the reported results in the original paper and highlight differences between the results and discuss, why they may have happened.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. In section 2 we will discuss how this project can be run and what needs to be setup before the project will start. Section 4 compares the reported results, with the results of the reproduced results and performs a

significance test. Finally, Section 5 concludes this work with a short discussion of the obtained results.

2 SETUP

The code and all further dependencies related to the experiment were made available via GitHub¹ under the user mickeystroller and can be cloned into an arbitrary directory. The setup and recreation process is carried out based on the instructions made in the README.md of mentioned repository and is extended by further information of the authors of this report, where information is missing.

2.1 Requirements

Before starting the actual experiment, few requirements are supposed to be downloaded and installed locally.

- Elasticsearch 5.4.0²
- Python 3³, with
 - elasticsearch 5.4.0
 - textblob 0.13.0

2.1.1 Installing Elasticsearch. Elasticsearch can be downloaded as ZIP file via the given link in section 2.1. Unpack the ZIP into an arbitrary folder and navigate into the 'config' folder and add the following two lines to the elasticsearch.yml file:

```
+ script.inline: true
+ script.indexed: true
```

Listing 1: Configuring elasticsearch.yml

Note that the download is a tar.gz folder and might further require an adequate unpacking program to retrieve all contents (i.e. WinRAR or others).

The first parameter enables Elasticsearch to use scripts, coded in 'Painless', a scripting language that can be used everywhere within elasticsearch.⁴ These scripts are needed in order to execute the proposed SetRank algorithm later.

The elasticsearch can be started in the bin folder typing one of the following lines in the terminal:

```
elasticsearch
elasticsearch.bat
elasticsearch.sh
```

Listing 2: Starting elasticsearch

¹<https://github.com/mickeystroller/SetRank>

²<https://www.elastic.co/downloads/past-releases/elasticsearch-5-4-0>

³<https://www.python.org/downloads/>

⁴<https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/master/modules-scripting-painless.html>

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2.1.2 Installing Python and dependencies. Python 3 can be downloaded as executable installer via the given link in section 2.1. After the installation, install the required dependencies via pip, the package manager of python. Therefore open the command line, navigate into the root of the downloaded git repository and run

```
pip install requirements.txt
```

Listing 3: Installing dependencies via pip

2.1.3 Creating Symbolic Links. In order to avoid I/O errors in script executions, a symbolic link should be created for the data/TREC-BIO folder. Therefore open a command line and navigate to the data folder inside the downloaded repository. Then create a soft link TREC_BIO which points to the folder TREC-BIO by executing

```
mkdir /D TREC-BIO TREC_BIO
```

Listing 4: Create symbolic link for TREC-BIO

This action is necessary as data folder inconsistencies are encountered in the original documentation.

2.1.4 Obtain data sets. Experimental results are computed for two benchmark data sets used for evaluating literature search, namely S2-CS and TREC-BIO. They can be retrieved at:

- TREC-BIO⁵
- S2-CS⁶

Both data sets should be downloaded at the stated links and placed into the data/TREC-BIO and data/S2-CS folder respectively to make them accessible for the python scripts.

3 REPRODUCTION

3.0.1 Reproducing effectiveness of leveraging entity information for ranking. The first part of the experiment is to calculate the scores for the baselines algorithms of Table 3 of the original paper [1], namely:

- **BM25** (Vector Space Model)
- **LM-DIR** (Query Likelihood Model, Dirichlet Prior smoothing)
- **LM-JM** (Query Likelihood Model, Jelinek Mercer smoothing)
- **IB** (Information-Based model)

Therefore an index has to be created for each of the baselines facilitating the elasticsearch algorithm. The necessary scripts to do so can be found under code/baselines. Open a command line and execute

```
python create_index.py - sim bm25
```

Listing 5: Index creation for bm25

and repeat this step for the other three baseline algorithms.

After all indexes are created, they are ready to receive data. Therefore execute

```
python index_data.py -sim bm25
```

⁵https://drive.google.com/file/d/1J6O9vm4wok4sEpV-1mVMWiNZ0_XIK7Xf/view

⁶<https://allenai.org/data/esr>

Listing 6: Index data for bm25

This task may take several minutes, depending on the size of the data sets.

Finally the retrieval of the baselines can be done automatically by running 'script.py' or manually by:

```
python search_data.py -sim bm25 -mode word
```

Listing 7: Performing retrieval with BM25, word

This results in a new .run file with added ranking information. The name of the file is made of the baseline algorithms' name and the chosen mode, either 'word' or 'entity'. Looking at 7 will generate the file bm25_word.run.

This file can be evaluated with pytreceval which calculates the scores for different rank aware evaluation metrics like NDCG (Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain), MAP (Mean Average Precision) and further. Therefore execute

```
./pytreceval/examples/eval.sh bm25_word.run
```

Listing 8: Evaluating results of retrieval

and find the resulting metric tables in the results folder.

For the TREC-BIO data set, the calculated scores for the baselines in all variations are identical to the results represented in the paper in Table 3 [1]. For the S2-CS data set on the other hand, some minor rounding errors occur. Still, the magnitude of the results is comparable to the ones from the original research paper.

For both data sets, the scores for the SetRank algorithm from the experiment reproduction differ significantly from the original results, which leads to the question, whether the reproduction process is faulty based on given documentation of the researchers. On the other hand, data manipulation could be a reason, but no accusations are intended to be made.

Conclusively, the hypothesis of significantly better results by the proposed new ranking algorithm by Shen et al. is not confirmed but rather questioned so far.

3.0.2 Reproducing Ranking performance on entity-set queries. In order to reproduce the scores for the data sets S2-CS-ESQ and TREC-BIO-ESQ, manual handwork is needed.

Jiaming Shen explains in 5.3.3 of the original paper [1] that there are 40 entity-set queries in S2-CS and 86 entity-set queries in TREC-BIO. These subsets are later used to evaluate the performance of SetRank and the baseline algorithms.

In order to reproduce the experiments where the TREC-BIO-ESQ or S2-CS-ESQ data sets are used, some files have to be modified in the following way. Open the file s2_query.json and

```

{"qid": "37", "ana": {"m/02tttd9": 1}, "query":
↳ "recommender system"}
{"qid": "38", "ana": {"m/0hj1w": 1,
↳ "m/01q0j8": 1, "m/06w4gk1": 1}, "query":
↳ "inverse reinforcement learning mixture"}
{"qid": "39", "ana": {"m/0b6vrv": 1}, "query":
↳ "transfer learning"}

```

Listing 9: s2_query.json

For every line, check the amount of entities in the ana object. If there are two or more entities, copy the line into a second file named s2_query_esq.json, which should result in a document with 40 lines.

Repeat this step for the TREC-BIO data set, again looking for queries with two or more entities and copy those 14 lines into another file named trec_query_esq.json.

These two files (s2_query_esq.json, trec_query_esq.json) should be used instead of the given files in the repository when calculating scores specifically for TREC-BIO-ESQ or S2-CS-ESQ.

To reproduce the scores presented by Jiaming Shen in Table 5 [1] of the original paper, the entity type information has to be modified. However, this step does not work in the reproduction due to KeyErrors at the execution step.

The following code fixes further need to be executed to continue reproduction:

```

- default="../../results/trec/setrank.run"
+ default="../../results/trec/setrank.run"

```

Listing 10: Change to fix naming of resulting .run file in results folder

```

- rankings = all_docno_rankings[query_id]
+ rankings =
↳ all_docno_rankings[int(query_id)-1]

```

Listing 11: Change to fix query parameter of autoSetRank_TREC.py

```

python autoSetRank_TREC.py -pre_saved_rankings
↳ rankings_reproduction

```

Listing 12: Change relative path in Line 383 of setRank.py

```

- choices=pytrec_eval.supported_measures,
+ #choices=pytrec_eval.supported_measures,

```

Listing 13: Comment in Line 20 of statistical_significance.py to enable t-test for NDCG {5,10,15,20}

4 EVALUATION

In this section we want to compare our results of the research, with the presented results of the paper and will also perform a two-sided t-test, to check if SetRank significantly outperforms the

Data set	Method	SetRank - Original			SetRank - Reproduction		
		Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both
S2-CS	NDCG@5	0.3890	0.3761	0.4207	0.399671	0.395124	0.399671
	NDCG@10	0.4168	0.3885	0.4431	0.415214	0.410436	0.41519
	NDCG@15	0.4411	0.4054	0.4762	0.436678	0.427663	0.436639
	NDCG@20	0.4674	0.4229	0.4950	0.455851	0.442817	0.455809
TREC-BIO	NDCG@5	0.3417	0.2111	0.3744	0.310815	0.271984	0.312328
	NDCG@10	0.3165	0.1976	0.3522	0.285773	0.245881	0.285678
	NDCG@15	0.3017	0.1931	0.3363	0.275616	0.23091	0.274014
	NDCG@20	0.2900	0.1885	0.3246	0.266475	0.222307	0.265842

Table 1: Comparison of reproduced results of SetRank with reported performance of SetRank. The best values are highlighted.

given baseline algorithms as stated in the hypothesis of the original paper.

Our results for SetRank need to be taken with a grain of salt, as the incomplete documentation does not allow us to exactly use the same setup as reported in the paper. As for example, it is not reported if we need to use Freebase or PubTator for linking the entities in the data set, as this has been done for the queries.

We focused our evaluation on the presented SetRank algorithm, as we have not been able to precisely know, what parameters need to be set to re-execute AutoSetRank, in the reported settings. This is why we cannot report, reliable results for this variant of the proposed unsupervised learning algorithm.

We have first reproduced the baselines for both data sets for comparison, if the data set and the queries were the same. We obtained the exact same values for all given baseline algorithms as mentioned in the original paper. Therefore we conclude, that we were implementing the algorithm on the same data sets and the same query sets as the authors, but we are unsure if we need to re-run the linking of the entities in the data set, with Freebase and PubTator, as this has not been documented by the researchers in 5.1. [1] Resulting inconsistencies in the facilitated data sets might be one reason for diverging results.

In table 1 we can see the presented results of the author on the left hand and on the right hand the best results obtained by reproduction of the experiment. All of the results use 5-fold CV to achieve the parameter combination. We can observe different behaviours, when comparing the different modes in which the queries have been executed. We notice better results for all queries, which use entity information in both data sets only. The word scores and overall scores are in all cases worse than the original reported results. This can be caused by differing specific tuning-parameters, which have not been set or have been set wrongly or due to the missing linking information in the data set. We have run the results with both versions, the tuning-parameters obtained by our execution and the reported tuning parameters, which are reported in Table 7 in the original paper[1], and used the best results.

Table 2 shows the results compared with the best baseline algorithm. The reported newly introduced unsupervised ranking algorithm in the paper has significantly outperformed all baseline algorithms. For reading purposes we will only reference the best baseline score. We observe that our obtained results are outperforming the baseline algorithms for the S2-CS data set like mentioned

Data set	Metric	Best Baseline	SetRank - Original	SetRank - Reproduction
S2-CS	NDCG@5	0.3759	0.4207*	0.399671
	NDCG@10	0.4039	0.4431*	0.41519
	NDCG@15	0.4272	0.4762*	0.436639
	NDCG@20	0.4421	0.4950*	0.455809
TREC-BIO	NDCG@5	0.3189	0.3744*	0.312328
	NDCG@10	0.2968	0.3522*	0.285678
	NDCG@15	0.2835	0.3363*	0.274014
	NDCG@20	0.2739	0.3246*	0.265842

Table 2: Comparison of reproduced results of SetRank with reported performance of SetRank and best baseline score. The superscript "*" means the reported model significantly outperforms all baseline methods (with p-value ≤ 0.05)

Dataset	Metric	BM25	IB	SetRank - Original	SetRank - Reproduction
S2-CS ESQ	NDCG@5	0.39939	0.395581	0.4983*	0.428076
	NDCG@10	0.436398	0.420853	0.5130*	0.447841
	NDCG@15	0.445422	0.449593	0.5450*	0.468901
	NDCG@20	0.460881	0.466399	0.5629*	0.487531

Table 3: Comparison of reproduced results of SetRank with reported performance of SetRank, using Entity-Set Queries. The superscript "*" means the reported model significantly outperforms all baseline methods (with p-value ≤ 0.05)

in the original paper, but performance is worse than the baseline algorithms for the TREC-BIO data set. In Section 4.1 we will analyze whether our presented results on the S2-CS data set still significantly outperform the baseline algorithms, even though they are 2-4% worse than the reported results.

When only using the entity set queries, as it can be seen in table 3, the difference between the reported results and our obtained results increases to around 7%. We only report the values for the S2-CS data set, as we have not been able to reproduce the baselines for TREC-BIO, as the correct splits of entity set queries and standard queries has not been documented by the authors.

As already mentioned, since some of the information is missing or not precisely documented, it has not been possible to reproduce numbers in the same magnitude as they have been reported in the paper. Consequently, our results for the S2-CS data set still outperform the given baseline and we further evaluate, whether this is a significant difference.

4.1 Significance Test

We state the following hypotheses:

$$\begin{aligned}
 X &= \{5, 10, 15, 20\} \\
 \text{baseline} &= \{BM25, LM - DIR, LM - JM, IB\} \\
 p - \text{value} &\leq 0.05 \\
 H_0 &: \text{ndcg}@X_{\text{baseline}} = \text{ndcg}@X_{\text{SetRank}} \\
 H_1 &: \text{ndcg}@X_{\text{baseline}} \neq \text{ndcg}@X_{\text{SetRank}}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

The scripts used for statistical evaluation are included in the mentioned `pytrec_eval` library⁷. Respectively the GitHub repository of the original experiment does also contain the scripts to run the `pytrec_eval` statistical evaluation. `pytrec_eval` features a function that computes the Student's t-test between a run and a list

⁷https://github.com/eXascaleInfolab/pytrec_eval

Data set	Metric	p-value with ndcg_cut_{5,10,15,20}
S2-CS (N=8541)	NDCG@5	0.187069991
	NDCG@10	0.338869011
	NDCG@15	0.327174910
	NDCG@20	0.132428707
TREC-BIO (N=4585557)	NDCG@5	0.02220377
	NDCG@10	0.03682268
	NDCG@15	0.53420820
	NDCG@20	0.45663744

Table 4: Statistical significance of our results, when being compared to the best baseline algorithm. All values with p-value ≤ 0.05 are significant and highlighted.

Data set	Metric	p-value with ndcg_cut_{5,10,15,20}
S2-CS-ESQ (N=8541)	NDCG@5	0.301073869
	NDCG@10	0.599354700
	NDCG@15	0.297369663
	NDCG@20	0.203376155

Table 5: Statistical significance of our results for the entity set queries, when being compared to the best baseline algorithm. All values with p-value ≤ 0.05 are significant and highlighted.

of other runs and returns a dictionary, mapping the name of run1 to the p-value obtained by comparing the NDCG score of run1 to the NDCG score of run0, and the name of run2 to the p-value obtained by comparing the NDCG score of run2 to the NDCG score of run0 and so on for further different runs (in our case the baselines).

To create comparability of results, the best baseline scores are chosen and compared to the score from the newly presented algorithm to check for significant differences. `graphicx`

Note that the significance level is higher for p values close to 0 and decrease the closer they get to the chosen significance threshold (here 0.05).

Further, significance differs due to the sample size N, which, as one can observe, is highly different for the chosen data sets. Therefore, the observed p-values show different significance for the two data sets, as it can be seen in table 4.

As expected, results for the S2-CS data set containing the whole queries, give the same intuition as in the original paper and yield slightly better results for the newly proposed algorithm compared to the best baseline. However, the significance of these results is not proven based on the results of the two-tailed t-test with significance level of 5%.

For the second benchmark data set, again containing all queries, all results from the best baselines outperform the SetRank algorithm. For two NDCG values, the newly proposed algorithm is even significantly worse than for the compared baseline.

For the entity query-set alternative, evaluation metrics have only been calculated for the S2-CS data set, due to splitting problems mentioned before. Regarding the new algorithm compared to the best baseline, and sample size $N = 8541$, the newly proposed algorithm has not been able to produce equally good results, while none of them are significantly worse, as can be seen from p-values in table 5.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have evaluated the reproducibility and the reported performance of the paper "Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach", by Shen et al. [1]. We can report, that the source code of this paper has been made available and is runnable with little adjustments, but the requirements have not been fully documented and it is necessary to adjust the code to obtain the correct results for different experiments. When reproducing the results of this experiment to the best of our ability, we have not been able to obtain similar values to those reported in the paper. We are able to state that our results for the S2-CS data set does not significantly outperform the baseline algorithms, as stated in the paper. For the other data set, TREC-BIO, the results are indeed significantly different from the baseline algorithm. In this case, this means that the performance is significantly worse. Due to inconsistencies in documentation and provided repository, proving the above for the second benchmark data set has not been possible. This leads to the conclusion that we can not confirm the hypothesis, that the newly introduced unsupervised ranking algorithm, is significantly better than state of the art facilitated literature query algorithms (represented in the paper as "baselines").

Our adjusted source code is available on GitHub, to allow the recreation of our experiments ⁸.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Xinwei He Jingbo Shang Saurabh Sinha Jiaming Shen, Jinfeng Xiao and Jiawei Han. 2018. Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach. In *SIGIR*. ACM.

⁸<https://github.com/JuLuk/ExpDesign>